

Studies on some Newer Simple and Substituted Indanyl Serotonin-3 Antagonist

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Serotonin (5HT) is a key mediator in various physiological as well as pharmacological responses¹. Currently four broad classes of serotonin (5HT) receptors are recognised² as 5HT₁, 5HT₂, 5HT₃ and 5HT₄. Of various serotonergic receptor subtypes, attentions have recently been focused on 5HT₃ receptor modulators mainly for their potential in various ailments³. Moreover, the 5HT₃ receptor physiology is well understood and suitable template for drug design is available. Thus based on original concepts on serotonin structure itself some 5HT₃ antagonists like ICS 205-930 and GR 38032F have already been established⁴. The well accepted key pharmacophoric elements of known 5HT₃ antagonists⁴ can be regarded as an aromatic moiety, a linking acyl group and a basic amine.

The present work is a part of a comprehensive study towards investigating the type of aromatic moiety necessary and the nature and distance requirement of end-amine system for 5HT₃ antagonism. It deals with design and synthesis of various indan-1-acid amides for their evaluation and exploitation as 5HT₃ antagonists. Thus, various substituted indan-1-acids were synthesised in a generalised method and their amides in turn were evaluated for 5HT₃ antagonism in standard guinea pig ileum model.

Results and Discussion

Polyphosphoric acid cyclisation involving various simple and substituted β PGA may be of valuable use towards a generalised cyclisation via simple dehydration. This easily adaptable dehydration cyclisation technique was fairly successful even with unfavourable aromatic substituents like 4-methoxy and 3,4,5-trimethoxy, and can profitably be utilised for preparation of various 3-ketoin-dan-1-acids. Resultant amides when subjected to 5HT₃ antagonism in guinea pig ileum studies it revealed that piperazine amides are considerably better active than benzimidazol analogous. Biological evaluation data (% inhibition \pm SE) of relevant indanyl amides in guinea pig ileum model are as follows: **4a**, 38.2 \pm 1.7; **5a**, 21.6 \pm 2.1; **4b**, 36.2 \pm 1.4; **5b**, 22.5 \pm 2.2; **4c**, 32.4 \pm 2.8; **5c**, 20.1 \pm 2.6; **4d**, 22.4 \pm 2.9; **5d**, 17.8 \pm 2.1; **4e**, <15; **5e**, <15; ondasetron, 39.3 \pm 1.8. Thus early postulate of 5HT₃ antagonist structural requirement of aromatic ring, carbonyl function and a basic center hold good in both piperazine as well as benzimidazol amides. However, relative basicity of the rigid end-nitrogen may have some bearing on 5HT₃ antagonist activity. Contribution of aromatic ring substituent towards

5HT₃ antagonism may also be of relevance.

Serotonin-3-antagonism activity: Male guinea pig (Charles River; 200–400 g) was killed by cervical dislocation. Longitudinal section of ileum (2–3 cm) was mounted in organ bath containing modified Krebs solution⁵ (40 ml) with continuous aeration and temperature controlled at 37°. Each tissue was placed under optimum resting force and allowed to equilibrate for ~45 min before exposure to drugs. Isometric tissue contraction against bath concentration of 0.04 μ g ml⁻¹ of 2-methylserotonin (agonist), was recorded in presence of vehicle alone and 0.4 μ g ml⁻¹ bath concentration of each antagonist (standard and synthetic compound)⁶. A set of six experiments were carried out for each compound tested and the average was recorded. Percentage inhibition of agonist contractibility for fixed dose of antagonist was recorded.

Scheme 1 Reagents: (i) ethyl acetoacetate: piperidine (1 : 2), (ii) KOH/H⁺, (iii) PPA/ Δ , (iv) Zn-Hg/HCl, (v) SOCl₂, piperazine and (vi) SOCl₂, benzimidazole.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis, Ir spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 270-30 spectrometer, electronic spectra on a Hitachi U2000 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a AEI MS30 instrument.

A mixture of the relevant aldehyde (1 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (2 mol) and catalytic amount of piperidine was kept enclosed at 30–40° for 3 days. The solid obtained was then washed with ether and hydrolysed by refluxing in ethanolic KOH solution. Ethanol was then removed and the mixture was cooled in ice followed by acidification with HCl. The resulting phenylglutaric acid (1) was then crystallised from water.

Compound 1 was mixed with appropriate amount of polyphosphoric acid and the mixture was warmed with occasional shaking on an oil-bath for required time and temperature. The cyclised keto product (2) was then extracted in chloroform.

Compound 2 (0.211 mol) was slowly added to a mixture of zinc amalgam (160 g; prepared from acid washed granular zinc, HgCl₂ and few drops of HCl), water (200 ml), concentrated HCl (200 ml) and benzene (100 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 6–8 h until the aqueous layer showed negative test for keto group. The benzene layer was then separated, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and evaporated to obtain the corresponding indan-1-yl acid (3) which was crystallised from suitable solvent.

Indan-1-acetylpiperazine/benzimidazole amide (4a,5a) : A mixture of indan-1-acetic acid⁷ (0.11 mol, 19.4 g) in sufficient amount of anhydrous benzene and thionyl chloride (0.3 mol, 35.7 g) was refluxed for 45 min. The excess thionyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure by co-distillation with benzene. The resulting acid chloride was then purified by vacuum distillation at 120° (1.5 mm Hg), (18.74 g, 87.4%). A solution of piperazine (0.2 mol, 17.2 g) in anhydrous benzene (50–100 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of indan-1-acetic acid halide (0.18 mol, 35.01 g) in dry benzene and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 30 min. It was then extracted in benzene, washed successively with aqueous alkali, water, aqueous acid and water and dried over Na₂SO₄. Removal of the solvent provided the corresponding amide (4a). The crude amide was then converted to the corresponding hydrochloride salt and crystallised from ethanol/water, (40.25 g, 80%), m.p. 120° (HCl) (Found : N, 10.01. Requires : N, 10.02%); ν_{\max} 3 508, 1 630, 1 436, 792 cm⁻¹.

Indan-1-acetylbenzimidazole amide (5a) : It was synthesised following the same procedure using benzimidazole as amine part, (78%), m.p. 48–50° (HCl) (Found : N, 8.85. Requires : N, 8.96%); ν_{\max} 2 960, 1 724, 1 396, 1 234, 756 cm⁻¹.

6-Methoxyindan-1-acetylpiperazine/benzimidazole amide (4b,5b) : The same procedure was followed as above : acid halide (78%), b.p. 142–45° (1.5 mm Hg); amide (4b; 80%) m.p. 55–60° (HCl) (Found : N, 9.1. Requires : N, 9.05%); ν_{\max} 3 444, 2 940, 1 628, 1 438, 1 248, 1 024 cm⁻¹; amide (5b; 75%), m.p. 80° (HCl) (Found : N, 8.19. Requires : N, 8.18%); ν_{\max} 3 456, 1 636 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 229, 294 nm.

5-Methoxyindan-acetylpiperazine/benzimidazole amide (4c,5c) : The same procedure was followed as before : acid halide (78%), b.p. 150° (0.5 mm Hg); amide (4c; 72%), m.p. 160° (HCl) (Found : N, 9.01. Requires : N, 9.05%); ν_{\max} 2 932, 1 638, 1 426, 1 252 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 274 (M⁺), 187, 160, 146; amide (5c; 70%), m.p. 40° (Found : N, 8.2. Requires : N, 8.18%); ν_{\max} 2 932, 1 700, 1 248, 1 030, 830, 746 cm⁻¹.

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-acetylpiperazine/benzimidazole amide (4d,5d) : The same procedure was followed as above : amide (4d; 80%), m.p. 230–32° (Found : N, 9.22. Requires : N, 9.21%); ν_{\max} 2 940, 1 626, 1 216 cm⁻¹; amide (5d; 76%), m.p. 150° (HCl) (Found : N, 7.49. Requires : N, 7.52%); ν_{\max} 3 312, 2 960, 1 722, 1 606, 850 cm⁻¹.

4,5,6-Trimethoxyindan-1-acetylpiperazine/benzimidazole amide (4e,5e) : The same procedure was followed as above : acid halide (72%), b.p. 182° (0.5 mm Hg); amide (4e; 70%), m.p. 74–5° (HCl) (Found : N, 7.61. Requires : N, 7.58%); ν_{\max} 2 940, 1 638, 1 414, 1 198, 1 112, 850 cm⁻¹; amide (5e; 65%), m.p. 82° (HCl) (Found : N, 6.89. Requires : N, 6.96%); ν_{\max} 3 432, 2 940, 1 676, 1 468, 1 114, 1 026 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 230, 293 nm.

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